

D4.5: Second period dissemination report and third period dissemination plan

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Document History

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on dissemination activity in ARIADNE during months 19 to 36, referenced against the second dissemination plan (D4.3), and also contains an update of the project dissemination plan for the final period, months 37 to 48.

The mission of the ARIADNE is to bring together and integrate existing archaeological research data infrastructures, so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new technologies as an integral part of archaeological research methodology.

The previous dissemination plans (D4.2 and D4.3) set out a strategy to raise awareness about the ARIADNE project and the research infrastructure amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
- Research institutions represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties including deans, directors etc.;
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines and the wider scientific community;
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

This aim will continue to the end of the project and beyond as the ARIADNE Infrastructure becomes established and more widely known and used by the archaeological research community.

The objectives of the dissemination plan for period two were to:

- Continue identifying the main channels for communication and networking with the stakeholder community;
- Build and extend the contact database by clustering with other projects, participation in events and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts;
- Informing the stakeholder community about news, events, training and trans-national access opportunities by producing the project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels as well as traditional media;
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, a brochure and other materials for use by the partners;
- Presenting the project at relevant national and international events.

Section 2 of this report describes dissemination activity during months 19 to 36 including how stakeholders have been involved in the project, the dissemination materials produced, dissemination of news and information, activity on the social networks and the project website, events, publications and activities around transnational access and training. Monitoring of the objectives and success indicators set in the initial dissemination plan show that targets were met and in most cases exceeded. The involvement of end users in workshops and summer schools has continued to grow.

Section 3 of this report provides an update of the project dissemination plan for period 3; this update takes into account the results of activities during period 2. During period 3, the aims of the dissemination strategy will be to:

- Communicate the project's **results** to stimulate interest in the infrastructure;
- Coordinate partner dissemination activities to maximize **impact**;
- Support the development of the ARIADNE **community**;
- Promote the **culture of sharing and collaborative** use of archaeological data;
- Communicate the ARIADNE **innovation agenda** and action plan.

The dissemination plan describes a range of activities to support these objectives.

2 Dissemination activity during the second period

This section of the report provides a review of dissemination activity during months 19 to 36 against the Second dissemination plan (D4.3).

2.1 Stakeholders

The initial dissemination plan (D4.2, pages 9-11) defined the following groups amongst the ARIADNE stakeholder community:

- Internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research or management responsibilities relating to project activities;
- Research institutions active in the field as represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties such as deans, directors etc.;
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines, field archaeologists and the wider scientific community;
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

During the second period, ARIADNE has continued to raise awareness of the project amongst each of these groups. This has been achieved by updating the website and tweeting regularly, the Newsletters, presenting papers and organizing workshops at national and international conferences, publishing project deliverables, presentations and other materials on SlideShare and other related dissemination activities such as poster sessions, videos on YouTube etc. In terms of website visitors, newsletter subscribers and twitter reach, the numbers have at least doubled during the second period.

Special Interest Groups have been established by work package 2 for project partners and external experts with an interest in:

- 3D and Visualisation
- Archaeological Research Practices and Methods
- Remote Sensing and Spatial Data
- Scientific Data
- Excavation and Monument Data
- Grey Literature
- Metadata and Semantics
- Linked Data

These groups met, in person and virtually, surveying the state-of-the-art in their field, exchanged information, identified issues and planned future activities. A section of the ARIADNE project website has been set up to hold information about the Special Interest Groups: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Community/Special-Interest-Groups>.

During 2015, ARIADNE launched Trans National Access (TNA) to online services offered by three partners:

- Archaeology Data Service: ARCHSEARCH.
- AIAC (the International Association for Classical Archaeology): FASTI Online
- Deutsches Archäologisches Institut: ARACHNE and ZENON.

The first ARIADNE service, the Visual Media Service, had a ‘soft’ launch in January 2015 – users were invited to use the service and provide feedback.

Events have been organized by ARIADNE partners for researchers and students to provide an introduction to the online services. Training workshops were held at EAA 2014 and CAA 2014. ARIADNE services were presented at the “Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures for Cultural Heritage” conference in Rome in 2014, and an ARIADNE conference session at CAA 2015. A workshop was held at Digital Heritage 2015 on 3D HOP and the Visual Media Service.

Physical access to ARIADNE TNA services was launched in 2014. A series of training events were held at EVA 2014, EAA 2014 and MEAT Paestum 2014 to introduce the physical TNA opportunities. The call for applications for TNA in the second year was launched in winter-spring 2015 with three summer schools (on 3D Documentation and the design of Archaeological Datasets) taking place and opportunities for individual research visits on the CIDOC-CRM and Scientific Archaeological Datasets at five TNA centres. The call for access was advertised internationally to researchers and advanced-level students via mailing lists. Two data management training workshops (in Vienna and Ljubljana) were held in January 2016.

ARIADNE has been actively engaging with **international networks** and research **infrastructures** from its launch. DCH-RP (Digital Cultural Heritage Roadmap for Preservation), DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), EHRI (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure), CENDARI (Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure) and the European Association of Archaeologists were involved in the ARIADNE’s launch event. DARIAH, CENDARI and CLARIN (Language Studies) all participated in the Research Infrastructures conference in Rome in 2014. The projects regularly exchange news and support each other’s dissemination activities.

ARIADNE has exchanged cooperation agreements with research institutions and projects:

- CENIEH, Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, Spain
- CNRS-FRANTIQ, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
- IAI-UJA, Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Arqueología Ibérica. Universidad de Jaén, Spain
- IAPH, Archaeological Institute of the Andalusian Heritage, Spain
- MCH, Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo, Norway
- DGPC, Direção-Geral do Património Cultural, Portugal
- AU, Aarhus University, Denmark
- IBC - Institute of Cultural Heritage, Regione Emilia Romagna, Italy
- SSCol - Soprintendenza Speciale per il Colosseo, Il Museo Nazionale Romano e l'Area Archeologica di Roma

- FSI, Fornleifastofnun Íslands
- VU - VU University Amsterdam
- SITAVR - Dipartimento TeSIS e di Informatica di Verona
- IAA - Israel Antiquities Authority, Israel
- UU - University of Umea, Sweden
- EAGLE project
- DCH-RP
- FAIMS (Federated Archaeological Information Management Systems), Australia
- Digital Antiquity and tDAR (the Digital Archaeological Record), USA.

A collaboration agreement is currently under discussion with the Département du Patrimoine, Direction de l'Archéologie, Belgium.

2.2 Resources amongst the consortium and externally

The ARIADNE consortium consists of partners in sixteen countries including Sweden, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria. The partners have continued to be very active in disseminating news about the project. Activities have included:

- Giving presentations at national and international events (see below for details)
- Organizing ARIADNE workshops at international conferences (see below for details)
- Distributing ARIADNE dissemination materials
- Distributing notices about ARIADNE activities to mailing lists
- Writing articles about ARIADNE activities for in-house newsletters
- Writing to individual CH institutions about the project
- Contributing articles to the ARIADNE newsletter
- Disseminating news and information about ARIADNE via the social networks
- Participating in meetings organized by research infrastructures, projects and international initiatives and giving presentations about ARIADNE and/or distributing materials.

2.3 Information and news

The project has continued to disseminate information and news about the project's activities and related areas via the project website, a project newsletter, social media channels and (to a more limited extent) to the press. During the second reporting period, a wider range of content has been added, leading to a redesign of the News page to enable users to distinguish between the different news channels. Now all the regular news items appear in the main panel and Partner reports (e.g. about Conferences or workshops), Media reports, the Newsletters and Press (Press releases and other information aimed at the press) each have their own sub-folder.

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website's news section. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Services', 'Community', 'Events', 'Resources', and 'News'. Below this, the 'News' section is active, displaying a list of recent news items. The first item is 'ARIADNE at CAA2016' dated 12 Feb 16, with a brief description of a session at CAA2016 in Oslo. The second item is 'CAA Recycle Award' dated 9 Feb 16, featuring a circular logo with 'caa recycle' and text about an annual award for data re-use. The third item is 'Data in libraries - Call for papers (IFLA)' dated 26 Jan 16, with a logo for 'IFLA WLIC 2016' and text about the 82nd IFLA General Conference and Assembly in Columbus, Ohio. On the right side, there is a sidebar with links for 'Partner reports', 'Media reports about us', 'ARIADNE newsletter', and 'Press', along with social media sharing icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter.

The main section is used to publish short news articles and announcements (such as calls for papers and participation in events): <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News>. In addition, news posted on the project's Twitter account is published on the home page of the project's website.

2.3.1 Project newsletter

A further three issues of the project newsletter have been published during the second project period:

- November 2014
- May 2015
- October 2015

Each issue of the newsletter has highlighted activities by ARIADNE, partner activities and related projects and initiatives such as the Open Access Repository Ranking and the Linked Pasts event.

During the second period, the mailing list has more than doubled to 326 subscribers who have registered on our mailing list and indirectly via notices to mailing lists and on Twitter. The most recent edition had a 44% open rate with 19 click-throughs to the website, the most popular of these being to the TNA training call.

The newsletters are available from the project website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/Newsletters>.

2.3.2 Social networks

Twitter

@Ariadne_Network was established on Twitter in April 2013. By 31st January 2016, activity had more than doubled from the first 18-month period:

- 508 followers (up 300 from 208)
- @Ariadne_Network is following 228 Twitter users (previously 103)
- @Ariadne_Network had made 1,110 Tweets since the start of the project, i.e. 790 during the 2nd period).

The graph (from <http://www.twitonomy.com/>) for the date range 18 April 2013 to 08 Feb 2016 shows a marked increase in Twitter activity, especially during the Infrastructure conference in November 2014 in Rome and thereafter. The peak in early April 2015 coincides with CAA in Siena, Italy where there were several ARIADNE –related papers and presentations given.

One hundred and Sixty three of ARIADNE’s tweets have been retweeted during the 2nd period (up from sixty). (Source Retweet.co.uk).

The top 10 Re-tweets for the 2nd 18-month reporting period shows there was a high level of interest in papers for international conferences, the Open Access session at EAA and training opportunities.

Rank	Subject matter	No. of retweets	Date
1	Call for papers on digital infrastructures for cultural heritage	22	26 Nov 2015
2	Call for TNA 2014 Open	10	17 Dec 2015
3	EAA 2014 Open Access session presentations available	9	19 Sept 2014
4	Call for papers on reuse of archaeological datasets at CAA 2016	9	8 Oct 2015
5	It's about time: historical periodization and Linked Ancient World Data	9	21 April 2015
6	EAA 2014 Istanbul: Programme for Open Access Session on Sat 13 th published	8	4 Sept 2014
7	Interested in the digital curation of archaeology knowledge? (TNA related)	8	17 Dec 2015
8	Rocky road to Open Access	8	13 Oct 2015
9	The Call for Papers for EAA 2016 is open	8	6 Jan 2016
10	CFP now open CAA2015 @ARIADNE_Network session "Supporting researchers use and re-use of archaeological data"	7	18 Oct 2014

Likewise, the graph of mentions off the ARIADNE_Network also shows increased activity during key events mentioned previously – the two peaks in July may also be linked to a 3D workshop hosted by ADS in York and the Linked Past Conference in London later in the month.

The Twitter accounts for ADS (Update and Chatter), the Digital Curation Unit and DARIAH mention the ARIADNE Network frequently and many of the partners promote the project through their own organisational and personal accounts, as do many of the dedicated individual followers.

The potential reach of @ARIADNE_Network on Twitter (i.e. the network of tweeters and their followers) is now over 1 million Twitter users.

LinkedIn

A LinkedIn Group has been set up for the ARIADNE Network and currently has 39 members. The group has been relatively inactive as Twitter and SlideShare are more popular social media channels with ARIADNE.

Number of members: 39

Number of discussions: 28

Facebook

A Facebook group was established for ARIADNE in May 2015. The group has been used to post news and photographs from ARIADNE events.

Number of members: 23

SlideShare

A SlideShare account was set up for ARIADNE in July 2014 only one presentation had been uploaded to SlideShare. Since then, a further seventy-nine presentations and documents have been added, and there have been a total of 41,775 views since the account was launched. Over the last twelve months there have been a total of 25,751 views; the top viewed content over this period was the ARIADNE booklet, the ARIADNE report on Natural Language Processing and presentations on Archiving Archaeological data in Austria, Integrating archaeological data in the ARIADNE infrastructure and the ARIADNE project. The top countries for viewers were Germany, United States, United Kingdom, Italy and France.

The graph shows that there was increased activity on the SlideShare account during January 2016, which coincides with the Data Management training workshops in Vienna and Ljubljana.

Overall, since the SlideShare account was launched the 20 most popular documents and presentations are shown in the table below – the ARIADNE Booklet is by far the most popular item.

Ariadne Booklet: The Way Forward to Digital Archaeology in Europe	4043
ARIADNE introduction (presentation)	3056
ARIADNE: First report on users' needs	1920
ARIADNE: Report on project standards	1066
Open Data in Archaeology (presentation)	1026
A first attempt at describing, disseminating and reusing methodological knowledge in Archaeology (presentation)	945
Identify criteria and fundamental concepts in archaeology: the case of the archaeological site (presentation)	938
The ARIADNE project (presentation)	994
Open Access in Italy (presentation)	965
ARIADNE overview (presentation)	936
ARIADNE update (presentation)	905
Open Access of Research Data: the present and future situation in Germany (presentation)	901
Austrian archaeological data and archiving options (presentation)	841
"Archäologische Informationen" and Open Journal Systems. Chances and Possibilities of an Open Access Journal (presentation)	800
Integrating archaeological data: the ARIADNE infrastructure (presentation)	796
ARIADNE: First report on natural language processing	795
The Geographic Archaeological Information system of Rome: between IPR and privacy protection law (presentation)	689
Think big about data: Archaeology and the big data challenge (presentation)	687
Open Access and Open Data as Steps towards an Open Archaeology (presentation)	714
Open Data Publication: requirements, good practices and benefits	619

Number of views 41,775

YouTube

A presentation of the project ARIADNE - Conference 'kick-off' in Rome - February 7, 2013 was made available on YouTube on 6th March 2013 and has had a further 9 viewings during the second period.

URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9x1-4Ddux8E>.

Franco Niccolucci gave a presentation about ARIADNE at the event “Fostering the Transatlantic Dialogue on Digital Heritage & EU Research Infrastructure” at the Library of Congress, Washington, US in March 2015. (1:08 – 1:26). This has had 66 views.

URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PUKgu6dSvMM>

2.4 Dissemination materials

MIBACT-ICCU coordinated the preparation of a project leaflet in summer 2013; partners have distributed this leaflet at a series of events. An updated version of the leaflet is being produced for the final year of the project. A flyer advertising the 2015 TNA call was produced by 2Culture Associates for distribution at CAA 2015.

2.4.1 The ARIADNE Booklet

A 102-page booklet was produced and first distributed at the Infrastructures event in Rome in November 2014. This proved to be very popular and is also the most downloaded output from the project available on SlideShare.

2.4.2 Project website

The ARIADNE website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) was launched in month one of the project. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to stakeholders and to related projects. The public part of the website includes:

- About - the project, consortium and activities
- Services – Trans National Access, Online Services, Training opportunities
- Community – joining the network, special interest groups, associated projects
- Events calendar
- Resources – presentations, publications, links and other useful resources
- News – news stories, bulletins and newsletter

During the reporting period, new sections have been created on the website and new content has been added as materials have been produced and the project's activities have advanced. For example, the Services page had new sub-folders added for software tools made available to the project.

The website has been made available in English.

Project resources are published on the ARIADNE website in a dedicated section:

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

2.4.3 Web statistics M19-M36 (1 August 2014 – 31 January 2016)

Google Analytics was set up to record visits to the ARIADNE website as soon as the site was launched and all the statistics have been produced with this package.

Between 1st February 2013 and 31st July 2014, there were 15,066 sessions by 9,346 visitors. During the second 18-month period, the number of sessions increased to 24,328 by 16,656 visitors – an increase of around 61% in the number of sessions and 77% for visitors.

Visitor Comparison	1 Feb 2013 to 31 July 2014	1 Aug 2014 to 31 Jan 2016	UP ^ DOWN v
Sessions	15,170	24,328	^ 60.37%
Users	16,656	9,404	^ 77.12%
Page views	86,218	50,016	^ 72.38%

The visitor peaks in November 2014 can be attributed to the highly successful Research Infrastructures on Cultural Heritage, co-organized in Rome by ARIADNE and MIBACT, the Italian Ministry of Culture in the framework of the Italian EU Presidency semester, on 13 and 14 November. This event was widely covered in the Italian press and also in some Greek and German publications (see <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/index.php/News/Media-reports-about-us>). The figures for November 2014 indicate that the proportion of website visitors from Italy rose to 48% (from around 17% for this 18-month period).

English remains the first language for 40% of ARIADNE website visitors, Italian has increased from 14% to 17%, whilst German has dropped to 8% (from 13%) and likewise there are small reductions in the proportion of French (4%), Dutch, Spanish and Russian (all 1%) although Greek remains at 3%. Eastern European languages represent a further 1% with the rest of the one hundred plus languages spoken being distributed widely across the world.

Please note: While there are systems in place to prevent visits from site administrators being registered in the statistics (by IP and by website account), these systems are not 100% reliable and may result in inflated visit counts from the UK. It is also worth noting that Google Analytics does not record visits from users with

JavaScript disabled. There are no accurate figures for the percentage of users with JavaScript disabled, but it is generally considered to be somewhere between 2% to 3%.

The geographic spread of ARIADNE website users is increasingly international. Europe is still the main source of visitors 73% (down by 11%) with a further 7% from North America. The share of Asian visitors has grown to 11% with a further 4% from Central and South America.

Percentage of visits to the ARIADNE website by country:

Top 10 referrers

ARIADNE referrals are still dominated by Social Media – Facebook and Twitter account for 22% of these. However, the publicity from the Research Infrastructure conference in Rome caused repubblica.it (online newspaper) to be responsible for 10% of all referrals. Other sources of referral were ADS (york.ac.uk, 5%) archeomatica.it (3%), an online Italian journal on the use of technology in cultural heritage, and FastiOnline (2%), two of which are archaeology services offered through the ARIADNE website. A number of the other partners also appear in the top 20 referrers, along with DARIAH.eu, another research infrastructure for the digital humanities. LinkedIn and SurveyGismo (the user requirements survey) have dropped down the rankings.

Referrals to the website lead to a total of 7,831 user sessions.

The following table shows the top 10 referrals (after the data has been cleaned to combine referrals from the same sources and the search bots have been removed).

Referral Source	Sessions	% Total
Facebook	1060	13.54%
repubblica.it	845	10.79%
Twitter (t.co)	740	9.45%
York/ADS	423	5.40%
archeomatica.it	229	2.92%
fastionline.org	192	2.45%
dans.knaw.nl	156	1.99%
v-must.net	149	1.90%
orea.oeaw.ac.at	147	1.88%
dainst.org	129	1.65%
Other	3761	48.03%
Total	7831	100.00%

The most frequently viewed pages on the ARIADNE site during period 2 were the Home page, the About page, the Call for Participation in TNA access for 2015, Resources and Services, much the same as for the previous period.

In total 49,667 page views were recorded during period 1. This increased to 86,218 during period 2.

Page	Page views	% Total
Home	12,669	14.69%
Services/2015-TNA-call	4,105	4.76%
Resources	3,691	4.28%
About	3,649	4.23%
Services	3,470	4.02%
Events	2,792	3.24%
Community	2,505	2.91%
News	1,976	2.29%
Online-Services	1,331	1.54%
ARIADNE-TNA-2015-Application-form2	1,200	1.39%
Other	48,830	56.64%
Total	86,218	100.00%

2.5 Dissemination activities

2.5.1 Events

Partners have participated in around 100 conferences and events during the second 18 months of the project. These activities include the organisation of one-day workshops, conference sessions, the presentation of individual papers and posters, invited talks and key-note speeches, distribution of project literature, and face-to-face meetings with representatives of networks, projects and organisations to discuss collaboration agreements. The full list of activities is presented in Annex 2, a few highlights are:

ARIADNE being presented at the Research Infrastructures conference, Rome, November 2014

- Workshop: TNA opportunities at EAA, 13th September, 2014, Istanbul.
- Workshops and presentation: Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures for Cultural Heritage, 13th-14th November 2014 at Biblioteca Nazionale, Rome.
- Workshops, Sessions and presentation of papers at CAA, April, 2015, Siena, Italy.
- Presentation at Linked Pasts, 21st July 2015, London
- Presentation at EAA, 3rd September, 2015, Glasgow, UK
- Workshop: Extending, Mapping and Focusing the CRM, 17th September 2015, Poznan
- Presentations and poster sessions, Digital Heritage Conference, 28th Sept – 2nd October 2015, Granada, Spain.

PIN has had regular meetings with research infrastructures, projects and research institutions to discuss opportunities for collaboration. During the second period, Franco Niccolucci was also invited to present the project at the European Research Infrastructure event organized at the Library of Congress, Washington, US and then at Cultura Patrimonia, Mexico in December 2014. Other partners have been to Valparaíso, Chile and San Francisco, US to promote the project at international events.

MiBACT-ICCU, with support from PIN, organized an international two-day conference on research infrastructures in November 2014 as an official event under the Italian presidency of the EU. This included a day on ARIADNE; a booklet about ARIADNE was produced for launch at this event. There

was a high level of press coverage in the Italian national newspapers (online and printed) as well as other countries, along with social media which boosted the profile of the project greatly.

Partners continue to plan dissemination activities for the final period, which includes submitting papers and proposals for workshops and sessions to international conference committees for consideration.

2.5.2 National events

There have been a series of events organised at a national level (see the list of dissemination activities in Annex 2). Some highlights include:

- Risorse digitali e strumenti collaborativi per le Scienze dell'Antichità, 2nd October 2014, Venice, Italy (PIN),
- Austrian Days of Digital Humanities from ACDH at OEAW, 2nd December 2014, Vienna, Austria
- National Conference: Digital Archaeology, 21st April 2015, Amersfoort, Netherlands (KNAW_DANS)
- Awareness raising exercise with politicians (TD & Senators) of Ireland, 13th May 2015, Dublin, Ireland (DISC)
- L'integrazione dei dati archeologici digitali. Esperienze e prospettive in Italia, 1-2 October 2015, Lecce, Italy (PIN)
- Data Management Workshops, January 2016, in Vienna, Austria and Ljubljana, Slovenia

In addition to events, there have been further face-to-face meetings taking place at national level.

2.5.3 Publications

2015

Aspöck, E., Kopetzky, K., Horejs, B., Bietak, M., Kucera, M. and W. Neubauer (2015) "A Puzzle in 4D: Digital Preservation and Reconstruction of an Egyptian Palace.", Proceedings of Digital Heritage International Congress 2015, 28. Sept. - 2. Oct., Granada, Spain.

Aspöck, E. and A. Masur (2015) "Digitizing Early Farming Cultures. Customizing the Arches Heritage Inventory & Management System", Proceedings of Digital Heritage International Congress 2015, 28. Sept. - 2. Oct., Granada, Spain.

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2.5.4 Guides to Good Practice and Case studies

The first new full Guide was published in June 2015:

Brewer, Peter, and Jansma, Esther, "Dendrochronological Data in Archaeology: A Guide to Good Practice", available from:

http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/Dendro_Toc

A case study to accompany this guide will be produced in the first half of 2016.

Other guides and case studies are available from the Archaeology Data Service/Digital Antiquity, Guides to Good Practice series online at: <http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/Main>

2.6 Trans-national Access and training

During the period there has been dissemination activity to support the promotion of the Trans-national access and training being offered by ARIADNE. These activities have included disseminating calls for participation in training events, calls for participation in TNA summer schools, notices about the launch of online services, news items via the project newsletter, twitter and other social media, and creating content in the Services section of the project website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Services>.

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for About, Services, Community, Events, Resources, News, Partner Area, and Blog. Below the menu, the breadcrumb trail reads 'Ariadne > Services > Transnational Access'. The main content area is titled 'Transnational Access' and contains the following text:

ARIADNE is a research infrastructure funded by the European Commission's FP7 programme to bring together existing archaeological research data infrastructures. A range of services and opportunities are offered to archaeologists to enable access to the research infrastructure including online services, training workshops, access visits and summer schools.

During the period from December 2013 to October 2016, ARIADNE will advertise calls for proposals from researchers to apply for either individual access visits or to participate in summer schools at one of three research centres to conduct their research projects or case studies.

- **Legacy dataset design and implementation:** the design of archaeological datasets and thesauri, conversion of legacy datasets and data formats, CIDOC-CRM compliance, definition of metadata schemas, metadata mapping, semantic annotation, and use of standard languages such as OWL, SKOS etc.
- **Scientific datasets:** the design of scientific datasets, conversion of legacy datasets and data formats, CIDOC-CRM compliance

Research Centres

PIN – the Prato branch of the University of Florence is also a research agency operating in many fields. Since 2001 it has developed significant expertise in the field of archaeological applications and has advised institutions in Italy and abroad on the recovery of legacy data and conversion to updated data formats, inclusion in data portals, and the creation of archaeological datasets.

ISTI-CNR – the NeMIS Lab is part of the institute of the Italian National Research Centre devoted to ICT research and based in Pisa. NeMIS lab develops technologies for modelling access and handling of information, digital library services and services for information retrieval. ISTI-CNR currently offers services within formal education or education projects and digital library activities within the framework of European related projects.

DCU – the Digital Curation unit of the IMIS Institute of the Athena Research Centre in Athens is active in the field of digital curation. The Unit has expertise in the design of archaeological datasets and thesauri, conversion of legacy datasets, definition of metadata standards, international metadata standards, metadata mapping and in the use of OWL, SKOS and other standard languages.

CETI – the Cultural and Educational Technology Institute of the Athena Research Centre in Xanthi is a multi-disciplinary research organisation. Its Archaeometry Department focuses on the application of advanced analytical physicochemical methods for the extraction of information from raw materials, archaeological artefacts, works of art, monuments and sites. The department's state-of-the-art laboratory covers archaeological dating and authentication, X-ray and radiation applications in culture, chemical analysis (organic and inorganic) and electron microscopy. The Cultural Heritage Department has developed significant expertise in the study of ceramics, the scientific documentation of artefacts and interpretation of archaeological data.

The sidebar on the right contains a list of links: Training Materials, Online Services, Software tools, Transnational Access (highlighted), 2016 TNA Call, User Selection Panel, How to apply, Application form, User feedback report, 2014 TNA call, 2015 TNA Call, TNA 1st Year Feedback, and a social media share button.

2.6.1 Physical access

As part of its Transnational Access (TNA) activities for the second period, the ARIADNE project advertised a call for researchers to participate in TNA, to carry forwards their own research. The opportunities were:

- Mapping existing datasets to the CIDOC CRM; individual training at PIN
- 2D/3D documentation for archaeology, 22-26 June, 2015, CNR-ISTI
- Design of archaeological datasets, 6-10 July, 2015, CNR-ISTI
- Scientific datasets; individual training at Athena-RC, Xanthi
- Design of archaeological datasets, 28 June-3 July, 2015, Athena-RC Athens

There were three calls for applications which were advertised widely in Europe and internationally; the first call closed on 15th March 2015; the second call closed on 15th June 2015; and the third call on 31st October 2015.

Ten researchers submitted applications in response to the first call, nineteen researchers to the second call and eight to the third call. The applications were reviewed by an international selection panel whose members included:

- Gary Lock, University of Oxford and President, Computer Applications in Archaeology
- Laurent Romary, INRIA & HUB-IDSL and DARIAH
- Peter Biehl, SUNY Buffalo, and European Association of Archaeologists
- Franco Niccolucci, PIN, Project Coordinator
- Julian Richards, ADS, Deputy Project Coordinator
- Achille Felicetti, PIN
- Carlo Meghini, CNR
- Roberto Scopigno, CNR
- Nestor Tsirliganis, Athena RC
- Costis Dallas, Athena RC

Twenty-eight researchers took up offers of TNA bursaries in 2015:

Name	Institution	Country of Institution	Nationality	TNA
Orla-Peach Power	University College Cork	Ireland	Irish	3D
Adela Kovaks	National Museum of Eastern Carpathians	Romania	Romanian	3D
Michael Ann Bevivino	Discovery Programme	Ireland	USA	3D
Martin Duffy	University College Dublin	Ireland	Irish	3D
Rens de Hond	Spatial Information Laboratory, VU University Amsterdam	Netherlands	Dutch	3D
Oscar Martinez Rubi	Netherlands eScience Center	Netherlands	Spanish	3D
Stefan Verhoeven	Netherlands eScience Center	Netherlands	Dutch	3D
Ian Moffat	Institute for Mediterranean Studies	Greece	Australian	3D

Name	Institution	Country of Institution	Nationality	TNA
Anja Masur	OEAW	Austria	German	CIDOC
Christophe Tuffery	INRAP	France	French	CIDOC
Aybuke Ozturk	Lumière University Lyon 2	France	Turkish	CIDOC
Amanda Karn	Uppsala University	Sweden	Swedish	CIDOC
Daniel Löwenborg	Uppsala University	Sweden	Swedish	CIDOC
Roberta Zeni	King's College London	UK	Italian	CIDOC
Giusi Sorrentino	The Cyprus Institute	Cyprus	Italian	CIDOC
Valentina Vassallo	The Cyprus Institute	Cyprus	Italian	CIDOC
Anaïs Guillem	University of Ljubljana	Slovenia	French	CIDOC
George Bruseker	ICS Forth	Greece	Dutch	CIDOC
Seta Stuhec	OEAW	Austria	Slovenian	CIDOC
Irene Petschko	OEAW	Austria	Austrian	CIDOC
Christina Reditou	The Cyprus Institute	Cyprus	Cypriot	Data, CNR
Edeltraud Aspöck	OEAW	Austria	Austrian	Data, CNR
Seta Stuhec	OEAW	Austria	Slovenian	Data, CNR
Laura Stelson	University of Bonn	Germany	German	Data, CNR
Ana Cláudia Silveira	Universidade Nova de Lisboa	Portugal	Portuguese	Data, CNR
Erika Cappelletto	Heidelberg University	Germany	Italian	Data, Athena RC
Ingrida Vosyliute	Vilnius University	Lithuania	Lithuanian	Data, Athena RC
Martin Duffy	University College Dublin	Ireland	Irish	Data, Athena RC
Isto Huvela	Abo Akademi University	Finland	Finish	Data,

Name	Institution	Country of Institution	Nationality	TNA
				Athena RC
Giovanni Fuso	University of Salento	Italy	Italian	Data, Athena RC
Laura Stelson	University of Bonn	Germany	German	Data, Athena RC

Feedback from one researcher, Roberta Zeni, who visited PIN in Prato for TNA on mapping legacy data to the CIDOC CRM was reported on the ARIADNE website:

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/Interview-with-Roberta-Zeni-on-Mapping-EpiDoc-to-CIDOC-CRM>

2.6.2 Online access

During 2014 ARIADNE launched Trans National Access to online datasets from three partners:

- Archaeology Data Service: ARCHSEARCH.
- AIAC (the International Association for Classical Archaeology): FASTI Online
- Deutsches Archäologisches Institut: ARACHNE and ZENON.

In 2015, the first ARIADNE online services became available – the Visual Media Service and Landscape Services. Links were added to these services from the Services section of the ARIADNE website. In addition to these services, two online services offered by KNAW-DANS were also linked to:

- KNAW-DANS Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology and
- The DANS e-depot repository service.

The launch of these services was promoted via news on the project website and via the social networks. The training workshops (see 2.6.3 below) also helped to promote the services to researchers and students.

2.6.3 Training

Training events are organized as part of the ARIADNE's TNA programme by UoY-ADS with support from PIN and other partners. During the second project period the following events took place at:

- TNA Opportunity Workshop, EAA Istanbul 2014 (10-14 September 2014)
- MEAT Paestum (30-31 October 2014)
- Supporting researchers in the use and reuse of archaeological data: following the ARIADNE thread, CAA Siena 2015 (30 March – 3 April 2015)

- Expert Forum, Athens (2 July 2015)
- Digital Heritage 2015, 3DHOP - Presenting Online High-Res 3D Models: a Crash Course (28 September 2015)
- Data Management Workshop, Vienna (19 Jan 2016)
- Data Management Workshop, Ljubljana (21 Jan 2016).

2.7 Monitoring indicators for period 2

Success indicators

Description		Month 36 target	Month 36 actual
Stakeholder involvement	No. of institutions	75 ✓	128 different institutions have been involved in ARIADNE. Several institutions have exchanged cooperation agreements with ARIADNE, many more have sent researchers for the TNA or participated in workshops or events
User involvement	No of participants	150 ✓	At least 1,000 users have participated in ARIADNE activities: C. 300 participants in workshop 48 participants in TNA 692 researchers and data managers participated in the user-needs surveys.
Project website	Visitors	9000 ✓	26,002 visitors to the website in 39,394 sessions between 1 st February 2013 and 31 st January 2016.
Research infrastructure online services	Anonymous users	400 ✓	1,331 visitors to the online services page of the ARIADNE website. 542 referrals from ARIADNE to online services by ADS, AIAC (Fasti Online) and DAI (ARACHNE); monitoring of these sites also show peaks in user activity related to ARIADNE events.
Research infrastructure online services	Registered users	400	Following discussion ARIADNE services are currently being developed without requiring users to register.
Social networks	No of	1000 ✓	508 Followers on Twitter. The impact of re-

	members		<p>tweeting of ARIADNE news by partners and other followers dramatically extends the reach to around 150,000.</p> <p>39 members on LinkedIn</p> <p>23 members on Facebook</p> <p>7 followers on SlideShare</p> <p>312 members on the project website.</p>
Presentations at international events	No. of presentations*	2000 ✓	<p>At least 4,479 users participated in sessions where ARIADNE was presented during period 2.</p> <p>The number of participants was reported by partners for c 58% of events. During the second period, 58 separate events were attended with 86 separate activities (paper presentations, etc.).</p>
Good practice guides accessed	No. unique visitors	1000 ✓	<p>755 unique visitors to Dendrochronology Guide to Good Practice</p> <p>197 unique page views to ARIADNE case study on Big data</p> <p>211 unique visitors to the Good Practices page on the ARIADNE website.</p> <p>24176 unique visitors to all ADS Guides to Good practice during the period.</p>
Newsletters	Readers	150 ✓	326 subscribers who receive the newsletter directly.

* This appears to be a mistake in the initial dissemination plan, as 1000 presentations over an 18 month period seems far higher than could realistically be expected in this kind of project. It seems likely that the intention was to set a target for participants.

Achievement of period 2 objectives:

Objective	Description & planned activity	2014-16 activity
Objective 1	Building the user base for the project website and portal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuing the development of the project website adding new content • Preparing for the launch of the integrated portal and registries 	<p>The website was established in the first month of the project and has been developed and improved throughout. The visitor rate has doubled in the 2nd period compared to the 1st period.</p>
Objective 2	Extending the stakeholder database: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuing to build the contact database • Developing the project's presence on the social networks. 	<p>The project has been continued to be active in disseminating news, participating in events and establishing collaborations with research infrastructures, institutions, EAA, CAA and others.</p> <p>Establishing the project's presence on Zotero.</p>
Objective 3	Informing the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities and transnational access to the infrastructure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuing to post news and information regularly via the website and social networks. • Producing the project newsletter • Increasing the availability of project presentations and documents via SlideShare. • Press notices 	<p>The project continues to disseminate project news, calls and other information regularly via the website and the social networks. Social media is driving traffic to specific pages on the website, for example the 2015 call for TNA access.</p> <p>3 issues of the project newsletter have been produced.</p> <p>79 presentations and documents have been uploaded to SlideShare during the period.</p> <p>A press notice was prepared to announce the Research Infrastructures conference in Rome.</p>
Objective 4	Informing the research community about transnational access and training opportunities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing the 2015 call to researchers to put forwards 	<p>External experts were invited to participate in the TNA user selection panel again.</p> <p>The 2015 and 2016 calls for TNA access were prepared and published on the project website. The calls have</p>

	<p>proposals for access.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of dissemination channels to advertise training opportunities to researchers. 	<p>been widely disseminated to researchers.</p> <p>Materials and user feedback from the 2014 and 2015 TNA have also been disseminated.</p>
Objective 5	<p>Developing the set of dissemination materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project brochure • Templates for case studies and fact sheets • Project poster 	<p>The set of project dissemination materials has been maintained and updated. Flyers have been produced for specific events and a second edition of the project brochure is in preparation.</p>
Objective 6	<p>Presenting the project at relevant international and national events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project presentations • ARIADNE Workshops and conference sessions 	<p>The project was presented at more than 50 international and national events during period 2, reaching more than 4,000 attendees.</p> <p>Conference sessions at CAA2014 and CAA2015 were very well attended.</p>

3 Dissemination plan for the third period

This section of the report provides an update of the dissemination plan (D4.2 and D4.3) taking into account the results of dissemination activity in periods one and two.

3.1 Dissemination strategy

ARIADNE is co-funded by the European Commission's Seventh Framework programme and started on 1st February 2013; the project runs for four years. It brings together partners from Sweden, UK, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria with the relevant expertise, combining excellence in archaeology, informatics and data management, as well as experience in research, innovation policies and international collaboration.

The overall goals of ARIADNE are to:

- Integrate existing archaeological research data infrastructures overcoming fragmentation and promoting interoperability, to create a Web of Archaeological Data;
- Build a community of researchers around the creation, sharing, use and re-use of archaeological data;
- Provide a common access point to distributed archaeological data centres supported by powerful new tools enabling visualisation and analysis;
- Create a new generation of researchers ready to exploit the research infrastructure by offering training and guidance;
- Stimulate new research avenues and innovation in the field of archaeology.

The aim of WP4 (good practices and dissemination) is to develop the consortium's strategy for effective dissemination of the project's results and the research infrastructure in the archaeological community, contributing to a vibrant community of use and providing best practice guidelines for exploiting the infrastructure within archaeological work.

The overall aim of the dissemination strategy is to raise awareness about the ARIADNE research infrastructure amongst:

- Research institutions, including managers and senior researchers with management duties (such as deans, directors etc.), research directors and institutional repository managers;
- Research projects including lead researchers and project data managers; Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines, field archaeologists and the wider scientific community;
- Data centres, subject/domain repositories, portals and online services;
- Research infrastructures and integrated services;
- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

The specific aims of dissemination strategy for the project in period 3 are to:

- Communicate the project's **results** to stimulate interest in the infrastructure;
- Coordinate partner dissemination activities to maximize **impact**;

- Support the development of the ARIADNE **community**;
- Promote the **culture of sharing and collaborative** use of archaeological data;
- Communicate the ARIADNE **innovation agenda** and action plan.

For the third dissemination plan period we have identified six main objectives, together with the corresponding activities (Table 1):

Objective	Description	2015-16 activity
Objective 1	Communicating the project's results	<p>Present the project at relevant international and national events.</p> <p>Deliver ARIADNE Workshops and conference sessions.</p> <p>Disseminate the availability of ARIADNE tools and services widely.</p> <p>Disseminate on open access and interoperability.</p>
Objective 2	Coordinating partner dissemination activities	<p>Make a set of dissemination materials available to all partners (flyers).</p> <p>Collect information about partners' participation in conferences and events, new publications.</p> <p>Disseminate partner's presentations and publications.</p> <p>Share partner's news via the website, twitter and other social media.</p> <p>Work with partners to maximize contacts through the partners' networks to disseminate news and build the stakeholder database.</p>
Objective 3	Promoting awareness of good practices and "next generation skills".	<p>Project website updated with resources, information material, presentations, links.</p> <p>Post news and information regularly on Twitter and LinkedIn. Continue working to increase the following.</p> <p>Disseminate Good Practices, Guides, training events, TNA opportunities and training materials widely.</p>

		<p>Produce 3 issues of the Project Newsletter and disseminate it.</p> <p>Share project presentations and documents to stakeholders via SlideShare.</p> <p>Press Notices – project international events, launch of integrated portal.</p>
Objective 4	Informing the research community about transnational access and training opportunities	<p>Prepare the third call to researchers to put forwards proposals for access.</p> <p>Use of dissemination channels to advertise training opportunities to researchers.</p>
Objective 5	Building the network	<p>Collaborate with related e-Infrastructures and projects – exchanging news, participating in joint events, bi-lateral meetings.</p> <p>Follow key innovators and stakeholders in the social media and sharing news.</p> <p>Disseminate news about the Special Interest Groups’ (SIG) activities.</p> <p>Disseminate news about opportunities for involvement by stakeholders in testing, commenting or contributing data to ARIADNE.</p>
Objective 6	Planning a media campaign	<p>Launch the integrated portal and registries.</p> <p>Prepare and distributing a press release.</p> <p>Communicate with the press.</p>

Table 1: Dissemination strategy

3.2 The stakeholder community

Different approaches are appropriate for different user groups. By developing an understanding of the needs and interests of each group, the project aims to make its dissemination activities more relevant to the people and organisations which we hope will be interested in using the research infrastructure and products such as the Guides to Good practice. Awareness of the needs of the community helps identify the best channels for contacting stakeholder groups (such as email lists,

conferences, other means) and in designing and planning dissemination materials and activities, and thus helps raise the visibility of the project.

The ARIADNE stakeholder community includes both direct stakeholders (the envisaged users of the infrastructure and its services) and indirect stakeholders (such as professional associations, policy makers and funding bodies). The initial dissemination plan defined groups of stakeholders (D4.2), these were updated to reflect work carried out during period 1 to prepare a “Users framework”. This framework distinguished four groups of potentially active direct stakeholders:

- Research projects including lead researchers and project data managers (level 1);
- Institutions including research directors and institutional data/repository managers (level 2);
- Data centres, subject/domain repositories, portals and other online services (level 3);
- Infrastructures and integrated services (level 4).

Other stakeholders who are also important for the project include:

- Internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research or management responsibilities relating to project activities;
- International networks, professional associations and related research infrastructures;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

3.2.1 Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines

This is the community of researchers, students and field workers active in archaeological research projects with an interest in scientific and technical approaches, and in creating, analysing, sharing, using and re-using archaeological datasets. This is level one of the ARIADNE user framework, for example an excavation project with a lead excavator, core team and associated experts. This group can be reached through conferences, events academic forums and publications. The message should underline the opportunities for using the ARIADNE research infrastructure, openness of data access, tools, innovation and potential new avenues for research.

Researchers are likely to be interested in:

- Data access and datasets; use of repositories and data centres;
- Tools and technologies;
- Forthcoming events, workshops and training opportunities;
- Research quality and innovation.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via scientific conferences and journals, dedicated publications and printed materials, regional and thematic events; training events and materials, etc.

3.2.2 Institutions

Institutions or centres are the umbrellas under which research projects take place. They include both research institutions and heritage management agencies. Research directors oversee and give

advice. Many manage an institutional repository where projects can deposit their archives. Amongst archaeological research institutions the emphasis will be on disseminating the potential for advancement in research quality, effectiveness of work and improvements in working practice particularly with regard to depositing and accessing data. The message should underline the advantages for individual institutions and researchers in collaborating with each other and contributing their data.

Managers and senior researchers within these institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the research infrastructure and its data centres;
- Opportunities for collaboration;
- Innovation, new tools and services available to researchers;
- Forthcoming conferences and events;
- Opportunities for training.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via dedicated web pages and leaflets, and via regional or thematic events.

Research institutions include universities, archaeological museums, specialist institutes, archaeology schools (such as the foreign archaeology missions based in Cyprus, Rome, Athens, etc.).

3.2.3 Data centres, domain/subject aggregators and service providers

Archaeological data centres have been established in some countries. Subject-based repositories and portals relevant to specialised areas of the archaeology domain are also available. Typically data centres support the research projects/individual research of many institutions within their country, while most domain/subject repositories are international, supporting research specialists from across many countries. The core stakeholders in these centres are the managers of these services. The emphasis will be on disseminating the potential for advancement in the delivery of integrated services particularly with regard to depositing and accessing data. The messages should underline the advantages for individual centres in collaborating with the ARIADNE research infrastructure.

Managers and senior researchers within these institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the research infrastructure and its data centres;
- Opportunities for collaboration;
- Innovation, new tools and services available to researchers;
- Forthcoming conferences and events.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via dedicated web pages and leaflets, and via regional or thematic events.

3.2.4 Research infrastructures for archaeology

These are research infrastructures active in disciplines related to archaeology or to the work of ARIADNE. This group includes both direct stakeholders (archaeology infrastructures with the potential to benefit from becoming accessible via ARIADNE's integrated services). This group has a

general interest in infrastructure developments and opportunities for networking, collaboration and sharing and exchanging news about activities and solutions being developed.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- the development of the infrastructure, tools and services;
- opportunities for collaboration and networking, such as international events and training events;
- Innovation, new tools and services available to researchers;
- Business planning and strategy development.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via the project leaflet, briefing papers and collaboration events.

3.2.5 Internal stakeholders

Internal stakeholders in ARIADNE partner institutions are one of the target audiences for the ARIADNE project, as it is important to disseminate to managers and decision makers within partner organisations to raise awareness of the project's activities and the opportunities for using the research infrastructure, both for their own members of staff/researchers and for their contacts and networks.

Staff within the partner institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the infrastructure;
- Innovation and the development of tools and methodologies;
- Best practices, guidelines and training opportunities;
- Data access;
- Conferences and other events;
- Advancement in research.

The aim of this dissemination activity is to make colleagues within the organisation aware about ARIADNE and its activities, to support and promote the development of the research infrastructure and to spread the news by capillary action within individual networks.

Internal stakeholders can be reached during internal meetings, through presentations of the project activities, by distributing dissemination materials and by sharing news.

3.2.6 International networks, professional associations and related research infrastructures

These are international networks, professional associations and research infrastructures active in related disciplines (e.g. DARIAH, CENDARI, Pelagios and others). This group is not a direct stakeholder of ARIADNE but has a general interest in infrastructure developments and there may be opportunities for networking, collaboration and sharing and exchanging news about activities and solutions being developed.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- The development of the infrastructure, tools and services;

- Opportunities for collaboration and networking, such as international events;
- Sharing and exchanging news;
- Business planning and strategy development.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via the project leaflet, briefing papers and collaboration events.

3.2.7 Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies

This group includes policy makers, for example, from national organisations with responsibilities for research institutions, funding agencies such as bodies with responsibility for funding research on a national level, and the European Commission. The individual representatives of this group typically have broad areas of responsibility, with archaeology being just one of many fields for which they have responsibility. The main message to this group is around the benefits and positive impact of the research infrastructure on a broad range of stakeholders and end-users.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- Business planning and strategy development;
- The socio-economic impact of the research infrastructure.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via policy briefings, which should be clear and concise for easy access.

3.2.8 Media and the public at large

The public at large are not direct stakeholders of ARIADNE but this group includes individuals with an interest in archaeology, research and in research infrastructures. Opportunities to inform this group about the work and innovations in research through the media and social networks should be exploited, not least because of public influence on policy-makers. Europeana is a potential channel for informing members of the public about ARIADNE and its data centres.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- General information about the project and the launch of new service;
- Archaeology in general.

The methods of communication with this group are the media (TV, radio and press), exhibitions and social networks (Internet, YouTube, Flickr). Dissemination materials include the project website, leaflets, press releases, images and movies.

3.3 Identifying resources

This section identifies the skills and experiences available within the project consortium, and their connections with projects, networks and associations.

3.3.1 Consortium

The best practices and dissemination work package is lead by PIN and involves all partners in the project consortium with support for the web environment from an external sub-contractor, 2Culture Associates Ltd.

The ARIADNE consortium consists of partners in 16 countries including Sweden, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria.

All project partners are responsible for contributing to dissemination activities including the identification of events, development of dissemination materials and to the development of the project website. Most of the partners have public relations departments in their institutions, or access to external resources, on which to draw relevant skills and experience for disseminating ARIADNE.

Responsibilities for dissemination activities:

- The coordinator, PIN and deputy coordinator UoY ADS together have strategic responsibility for coordinating dissemination activities by all partners.
- PIN leads WP4 and is responsible for managing the development of the project website as a one-stop access point to the integrated infrastructure and social network channels.
- PIN with the support of DISCOVERY are responsible for publicising the project and sharing news and information about project results through the project newsletter, social networks and media channels.
- All partners are responsible for publicising the project within their countries via local media and networks, translating dissemination materials into their national language(s) as appropriate.
- DAI and PIN are responsible for coordinating ARIADNE events in the framework of international conferences and all partners offer support as appropriate to the event planning.
- MiBAC-ICCU is responsible for coordinating publication activity.
- UoY-ADS together with KNAW-DANS are responsible for the identification, assessment and definition of good practices with the support of the other “archaeological partners” (DAI, Athena RC, Discovery, ZRC-SAZU, MNM-NOK, CYI-STARC, ARUP-CAS, OAW, NIAM-BAS, MIBAC-ICCI, ARHEO and INRAP) as required.
- UoY-ADS is responsible for coordinating the expansion of the existing online publication of a series of Guides to Good Practice; the project Steering Committee is responsible for approving material for publication; and individual partners are responsible for providing input according to their expertise.
- SRFG, with the support of PIN and UoY-ADS, is responsible for organising the stakeholder survey (in the framework of work package 2).
- DISCOVERY, with the support of DAI and Athena-RC, is responsible for coordinating the Special Interest Groups.

3.3.2 External partners and related international initiatives

ARIADNE has entered into cooperation agreements and has established associations with a number of external organisations and international initiatives/projects (section 2.1 above). A number of other organisations, projects, network and research infrastructures have also been identified. Some may enter into formal collaboration agreements with ARIADNE during period 2, while others may be interested in following ARIADNE's activities and in cooperating with the project on an informal basis by exchanging news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for ARIADNE will be to make contact with these organisations and initiatives, sharing news about project activities and to seeking opportunities for collaboration.

ARIADNE has formal collaborations with:

- CENIEH, Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, Spain
- CNRS-FRANTIQ, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
- IAI-UJA, Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Arqueología Ibérica. Universidad de Jaén, Spain
- IAPH, Archaeological Institute of the Andalusian Heritage, Spain
- MCH, Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo, Norway
- DGPC, Direção-Geral do Património Cultural, Portugal
- AU, Aarhus University, Denmark
- IBC - Institute of Cultural Heritage, Regione Emilia Romagna, Italy
- SSCol - Soprintendenza Speciale per il Colosseo, Il Museo Nazionale Romano e l'Area Archeologica di Roma
- FSI, Fornleifastofnun Íslands
- VU - VU University Amsterdam
- SITAVR - Dipartimento TeSIS e di Informatica di Verona
- IAA - Israel Antiquities Authority, Israel
- UU - University of Umea, Sweden
- EAGLE project
- DCH-RP
- FAIMS (Federated Archaeological Information Management Systems), Australia
- Digital Antiquity and tDAR (the Digital Archaeological Record), USA.

A collaboration agreement is currently under discussion with the Département du Patrimoine, Direction de l'Archéologie, Belgium.

Other external initiatives which been identified and where there are opportunities for informal cooperation and perhaps formal collaboration include:

- CARARE¹ (community: archaeology and built heritage)
- 3D-ICONS² (community: 3D digitization)

¹ <http://www.carare.eu>

² <http://www.3DICONS-project.eu>

- Europeana³ (community: cultural heritage)
- DARIAH⁴ (: research infrastructure for arts and humanities)
- CENDARI⁵ (: research infrastructure for medieval and modern history)
- EHRI⁶ (community: researchers in holocaust research)
- ArchaeoLandscapes, Pelagios, Pleiades, Galia Informations, CSIR (Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani) and European Archaeological Schools abroad (stakeholder community: archaeological research)
- V-Must⁷ (community: museums)
- LoCloud⁸ (community: digital libraries)

There is a close relationship between ARIADNE and DARIAH; ARIADNE is an affiliated project within the DARIAH network. The project envisages collaborating with and making use of the services offered by the DARIAH Virtual Competency Centres. The DARIAH virtual competency centre on Advocacy, Impact and Outreach will assist in disseminating ARIADNE results and interfacing with key influencers in the field.

More recently, the PARTHENOS Project which is establishing a research infrastructure for the humanities and which started in May 2015, includes representatives from all the above mentioned RIs from the Humanities including ARIADNE and also CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure).

It is envisaged that ARIADNE will have links with Europeana, which can have impact in stimulating the interest of the broad public audiences in archaeology and heritage, and in stimulating study visits to archaeological museums and sites.

The ARIADNE social networking team (PIN and DISCOVERY) will follow the international projects, initiatives and research infrastructures identified as being of interest via their websites, Twitter feeds and other social network channels.

Partner responsibilities:

- Within the framework of WP2, AIAC will be responsible for coordinating approaches to related international and national initiatives to avoid duplication and to maximum effect.
- PIN, KNAW-DANS and UoY-ADS coordinates liaison with related EU projects such as DARIAH.
- PIN liaises with the European Projects CARARE, 3D-ICONS, PATHS and LoCloud.
- CNR coordinates liaison with the Europeana foundation.
- Athena RC liaises with DYAS, the planned Arts & Humanities infrastructure for Greece.

³ <http://www.europeana.eu>

⁴ <http://www.dariah.eu/>

⁵ <http://www.cendari.eu/>

⁶ <http://www.ehri-project.eu/>

⁷ <http://www.v-must.net/>

⁸ <http://www.locloud.eu>

- MiBAC-ICCU coordinates liaison with public institutions and liaises with the European projects Athena-Plus, Linked Heritage and DCH-RP.
- AIAC coordinates liaison with Pelagios, Pleiades, Gallia Informations, CSIR and European Archaeological Schools abroad.
- DAI liaises with ArchaeoLandscapes and IANUS.

3.3.3 Groups and associations

Several ARIADNE partners are members of groups and associations active within the field. These groups and associations each represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for ARIADNE will be to explore opportunities to disseminate news and information about project activities with these groups.

The groups and associations that have been identified include:

- European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)
- Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) – contact = Cesar Gonzalez-Perez (CSIC) is CAA Membership Secretary
- VAST – contacts = Franco Niccolucci (PIN) - General Co-Chair and Achille Felicetti - International Program Committee
- Digisam Sweden – a network for coordination of digitisation, digital preservation and digital access to cultural heritage in Sweden – contact = Ulf Jakobsson, SND
- Association of Cypriot Archaeologists (ACA) contact = Sorin Hermon, STARC
- Society of Cypriot Studies = Sorin Hermon, STARC
- Historic Environment Information Resources Network (HIERNET) Julian Richards, ADS
- Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH) Julian Richards, ADS

3.3.4 Community building

Community building is fostered through the activities of work package 2, which during period 3 will include:

- disseminating the innovation agenda and action plan by publishing papers, sharing news, etc.
- Inviting stakeholders to give feedback on the initial innovation agenda and action plan to inform the final version of the plan.
- Continuing to support the Special Interest Groups (SIGs) in the research community with the aim of discussing the state of the art and issues relating to the creation and use of datasets. The individual SIGs will meet during the period (normally during existing conferences) and will continue to discuss and report on their areas. The SIGs are:
 - 3D and Visualisation
 - Archaeological Research Practices and Methods
 - Remote Sensing and Spatial Data
 - Scientific Data
 - Excavation and Monument Data
 - Grey Literature

- Linked Data
- Metadata and Semantics
- Publication of position papers by SIGs.
- Making use of online and social networking tools for discussion, to share news, calls for participation and information about resources made available on the project website.

3.3.5 Contact database

The objective for 2016-17 will be to continue to build the project's contact database by encouraging subscriptions to the project website and newsletter, followers on Twitter and membership of the project's LinkedIn group. Accounts will be established for the project in Mendeley, Academia.edu, Zotero and IAM Researcher, which are used by the academic community.

The strategies for building and extending the contact database include community building activities, such as carrying out the survey of stakeholders and developing special interest groups, as well as liaising with research institutions, related international and national initiatives, cooperation with groups and associations, disseminating news and updates about the project's activities through various channels, including direct contacts of partners' network, use of social media, project newsletter, partners' newsletters, press notices and by participating in conferences and events.

3.4 Informing the stakeholder community

The objective is to inform the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities, the development of the infrastructure and the availability of datasets, tools and services. This will be done through the different channels (project newsletter, mailing lists, social networks, press notices) documented below, as well as via project events, workshops, tutorials and other activities.

Our strategy is to make the initial approach the target audience by making use of social media, professional/personal/local contacts from the project partners' network, etc.

Contacts will be made through the use of an appropriate **message** to transmit information, which should vary according to the target audience. For example, when reaching the research community we could point out specific publications on the project website, news about forthcoming conferences or innovation in the archaeological research infrastructure.

During 2016-17 the editorial strategy for the project newsletter and news disseminated via the social networks will be to:

- Share news about the project's results, project activities and achievements.
- Promote calls for participation in ARIADNE workshops, training events and TNA.
- Promote the ARIADNE portal and online services.
- Share news about events organized by the project.
- Share news from affiliated organisations and projects.
- Share news from related research infrastructures and initiatives active in same area as ARIADNE.
- Promote open sharing and re-use of archaeological data.
- Share news about developments in the state-of-the art.
- Share news from ARIADNE (and related) special interest groups.

- Share news about opportunities and benefits for researchers and research projects.

3.4.1 News on the project website

Short articles will continue to be published on the project website alongside calls for papers and participation in events. News will continue to be disseminated via Twitter (see below) with the project tweet feed being published on the home page of the project website.

3.4.2 Project newsletter

The editorial strategy for the project newsletter during 2016-17 will be to create articles discussing ARIADNE services and related topics. A short version of the newsletter will be prepared for email distribution, this will continue to contain short excerpts linked to full news stories published on the project website. The aim of this approach is to drive traffic to the project website.

Four issues of the newsletter are planned during period three of the project. These will be distributed directly to stakeholders registered on our mailing lists and indirectly to email lists and via notices on the social networks. The full newsletter will be available on the project website.

3.4.3 Social networks

Twitter - Ariadne_Network

The strategy for **Twitter**⁹ during 2016-17 will be to:

- Post Tweets related to the project's activities (newsletter, events, the launch of new services) or information related to domains of interest to ARIADNE and its Special Interest Groups. This will keep followers informed about the project and activate new discussions around pertinent areas.
- Encourage the partners to share interesting news and then tweet them with the project hashtag #Ariadne_Network.
- Monitor events (who's attending what events) and tweet about the event with the event hashtag
- Involve ARIADNE project members who are active on Twitter to create interest around ARIADNE by Tweeting about the project (@Ariadne_Network) and retweeting any tweets of interest.
- Include the project Twitter feed on the home page of the project website.
- Follow relevant Twitter users. This activity gives the ARIADNE project visibility: some of these users might follow ARIADNE in return or retweet project tweets to their followers etc.

Partners will continue to be encouraged to tweet about ARIADNE in their national languages mentioning the project using @Ariadne_Network to enable re-tweeting.

⁹ <http://www.twitter.com/3Dicons>

LinkedIn

The strategy for **LinkedIn** during 2016-17 will be to promote discussion about ARIADNE and to support the Special Interest Groups and their discussions. The objective will be to increase the number of followers of the group(s) during the year.

A group has been established for ARIADNE at:

http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=4966050&trk=anet Ug_Hm

Among the list of relevant existing LinkedIn groups we identified:

- ArchaeoLandscapes Europe
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage Group
- CAA: Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology
- CARARE: connecting archaeology and architecture to Europeana
- CIDOC - International Documentation Committee of ICOM
- Computer Vision Technologies
- Digital Heritage Preservation
- Geomatics
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage
- Laser Scanning
- Laser Scanning Forum
- The LiDAR Forum
- Open Source LiDAR
- Photogrammetry & Laser Scanning
- Spatial Ireland
- Web3D Professionals
- WebGL Developers

SlideShare

A SlideShare account has been established for the project: ariadnenetwork. The strategy for 2016-17 will be to increase the availability of project presentations, reports and other publications that are available to users of SlideShare.

YouTube

A **YouTube** channel has been established for the project. To date this channel has been used to upload a single video. The strategy for 2016-17 will be to evaluate the potential to produce further videos suitable for uploading to this channel.

Zotero

A **Zotero** library has been established for the project. The library provides a bibliography of project deliverables, conference papers, journal articles, newspaper articles and web pages. The library is available at: https://www.zotero.org/ariadne_network/items.

Other media channels

- Flickr – this will be used to share photos of project events
- Mendeley
- Academia.edu
- IAM Researcher
- Partner’s websites
- Partner’s newsletters, blogs and news feeds

3.4.4 External Newsletters

Other newsletters which may take ARIADNE news, stories or short articles include magazines and newsletters produced by partners, affiliates, related initiatives and news organisations. Some possible publications are listed below.

Title	Description	Deadline
AIAC news	The newsletter of the International Association of Classical Archaeology http://www.aiac.org/en/aiacnews	3 issues per year
The European Archaeologist	The newsletter of the European Association of Archaeologists http://e-a-a.org/tea/	2 issues per year
ADS news	The newsletter of the Archaeology Data service http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/newsletter	1 issue per year
DANS news	www.dans.knaw.nl/en/content/news	Regular updates
GARR news	http://www.garrnews.it/ in Italian	Annual

3.4.5 Mailing lists

The members of the project team are each registered on various mailing lists for professional reasons. These lists cover different aspects of archaeological research, including specialist subject areas, uses of particular technologies, digital preservation, general topics in cultural heritage and digital libraries and business domains. Although many people subscribe to more than one mailing list, the full membership of each list differs.

The project is creating a document summarising relevant email lists. To avoid multiple postings, team members will be asked to take responsibility for circulating project news to specified mailing lists. Partners have been asked to identify which email lists team members are signed up to. A

master list will then be made to enable the dissemination of news items to the lists to be coordinated by PIN with support from all partners.

The strategy is to post notices about ARIADNE to the lists (for example to announce a new issue of the newsletter or a forthcoming event with a link to the project website). Such notices are a good way of driving traffic to the website and allow contacts the opportunity of registering on the website as users.

The work of sending notices will be done periodically according to the project activities and developments.

The email lists which have been identified include:

- ARCH-AC-UK - UK academic archaeologists mailing list: <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?A0=ARCH-AC-UK>
- ROSA - Slovenian archaeologists mailing list (ZRC SAZU)
- Musei-IT
- Associazione nazionale archeologi
- antiquist@googlegroups.com
- ADS News (ADS)
- Datalink (DANS newsletter) (KNAW-DANS)
- International Association for Classical Archaeology (AIAC's list)
- Society of Cypriot Studies (STARC)
- Association of Cypriot Archaeologists (STARC)
- Archaeological Research Unit-University of Cyprus (STARC)
- New Archaeological Research Network for Integrating Approaches to Ancient Material Studies- (NARNIA) - (STARC)

3.4.6 Press notices

Press notices and press releases are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: Newspapers or magazines (online or papers versions), news sites, news networks.

A press release will be prepared to announce the launch of the ARIADNE portal in late spring 2016.

A press section has been established on the project website as an information point for members of media organisations at: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/Press>

3.5 Dissemination materials

A set of dissemination materials has been produced for the project and this will be maintained and developed during period 3. The dissemination materials include:

3.5.1 Project website

The ARIADNE website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) will continue to be maintained and developed by the addition of new content during period 3.

The aim of the site continues to be to provide information about the project and its activities to stakeholders and to provide access to news, calls for participation, resources and services, including access to the ARIADNE integrated portal. The portal will provide a single point of access to the research infrastructure.

The public part of the website includes:

- About - the project, consortium and activities
- Services – Online Access, Trans National Access and Training.
- Community – Associated partners and projects, Special Interest Groups.
- Events calendar
- Resources – presentations, publications, links and other useful resources
- News – news stories, bulletins and newsletter
- Contacts

The website has been made available in English.

3.5.2 Project leaflet

MiBAC-ICCU, with support from PIN, will coordinate the preparation of a new version of the project leaflet, to present the project and its main activities and be made available for distribution by partners at events.

A project booklet will be prepared for distribution at the final project event.

3.5.3 Other dissemination materials

The basic set of promotional materials will be updated as appropriate during period 3. The materials include:

- A selection of images made available by project partners
- A set of project logos for use in printed materials and online resources, with branding guidelines and instructions for printers
- Templates for fact sheets, presentations etc.
- A project brochure
- A project poster
- An ARIADNE Essentials PowerPoint presentation.

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the Intranet of the ARIADNE project website. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by partners.

3.5.4 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Dissemination materials including reports, presentations, promotional material and publications must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag.

Example: "ARIADNE is a project funded by the European Commission under the Community's Seventh Framework Programme, contract no. FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2012-1-313193".

Any communication or publication shall state that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Community is not liable for any use that might be made of the information contained therein.

3.6 Dissemination activities

3.6.1 Events

This activity concerns participation by project partners in events including:

- Single project presentations at conferences or symposia
- Dedicated project sessions
- Workshops
- Tutorials or short training sessions
- Participation in exhibitions with a booth, poster or demo

A final event is planned for the end of the project; this will present the outcomes of the project.

3.6.1.1 *ARIADNE at international events*

DAI and PIN manage the logistics of project events taking place in the framework of larger events including contacts with the organisers, arrangements for participation, payment of fees and so on. PIN and UoY ADS together guarantee to provide a project presence at key events.

During period 3 ARIADNE plans to organize workshops, to deliver training and to give presentations at international conferences. The conferences where ARIADNE is planning to deliver sessions, round tables or other events include:

- The yearly Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) conference with an audience of around 400 delegates focused on IT in archaeology;
- The yearly European Archaeologists Association (EAA) conference with an audience of around 1,000 archaeological delegates;

The project's presence at such events may include workshops, sessions, individual presentations, posters etc. The aim will be to disseminate the project's activities and promote the opportunities offered by the research infrastructure to researchers and in particular to young researchers.

A set of dissemination materials will be prepared each year for use in international events. These will be made available online in English for translation into local languages as appropriate.

Potential international events

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
CAA 2016, http://caaconference.org	Annual international conference	Oslo, Norway	29 March – 2 April 2016
CAA 2016 session, http://caaconference.org/	Supporting researchers in the use and re-use of archaeological data: continuing the ARIADNE thread	Oslo, Norway	29 March – 2 April 2016
EVA London 2016 http://www.eva-london.org/eva-london-2016	Electronic visualisation technologies in art, design, music, dance, theatre, the sciences and more	London, UK	12-14 th July 2016
LAC 2016 http://www.arkeologi.uu.se/LAC_2016+/	3 rd International Landscape Archaeology Conference	Uppsala, Sweden	23-25 Aug 2016
EAA 2016 http://eaavilnius2016.lt/	22 nd Annual meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists	Vilnius, Lithuania	30 August – 3 Sept 2016
EAA: Open Access session	"Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology: Following the ARIADNE thread"	Vilnius, Lithuania	30 August – 3 Sept 2016
PECSRL 2016 http://www.pecsrl2016.com/	"Mountains, uplands, lowlands. European landscapes from an altitudinal perspective"	Innsbruck and Seefeld, Austria	5-9 Sept 2016
TPDL 2016 http://www.tpd2016.org/	Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2014)	Hannover, Germany	5-9 Sept 2016
NKOS workshop 2016	Annual European Networked Knowledge Organisation Systems and Services workshop, held at TPDL 2016	Hannover, Germany	5-9 Sept 2016
GCH 20146 http://gch2016.ge.imati.cnr.it/	14 th Eurographics workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage	Genova, Italy	5-7 th Oct 2016
Arqueologica 2.0 2016 http://arqueologica8.webs.upv.es/	8 th International meeting on Graphic Archaeology and Informatics	Valencia, Spain	5-7 Sept 2016
CIDOC 2016 http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/	Annual conference of CIDOC: Museums and Cultural Landscapes	Milan, Italy	6-11 Sept 2014
iPRES 2016 http://www.ipres2016.ch/	13 th International Conference on Digital Preservation	Bern, Switzerland	3-6 Oct 2016
EuroMed 2016 http://www.euromed2016.eu/	International conference on Digital Cultural Heritage	Limassol, Cyprus	31 st Oct – 5 th Nov 2016
CHNT 21 http://www.stadtarchaeologie.at/	Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies: Urban Archaeology and Processing	Vienna, Austria	16-18 Nov 2016
ICDH 2016	International Conference on Digital	London, UK	24-25 Nov

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
https://www.waset.org/conference/2016/11/london/ICDH	Heritage		2016
EVA Florence 2016	Electronic Information, the Visual Arts and Beyond	Florence, Italy	TBC
AARG 2016	Annual meeting of the Aerial Archaeology Research Group	TBC	TBC
VAST	International symposium on virtual reality, archaeology and cultural heritage	TBC	TBC
MTSR 2016 http://www.mtsr-conf.org/	10 th Metadata and Semantics Research Conference	TBC	TBC

Potential National events

ARIADNE is presented by partners at a number of national events each year. Some events coming up on national level during 2016-17 are listed below:

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
10 th ICAANE	“Old excavation data – what can we do?” Workshop on legacy archaeological datasets organized by OEAW	Vienna, Austria	28 April, 2016
CAA	CAA national chapters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAA-UK • CAA-Germany • CAA-Netherlands • CAA-Estonia • CAA-Greece • CAA-Norway • CAA-Poland • CAA-Sweden 	Various	Various
DHBenelux conference http://dhbenelux.org/	A yearly event to promote Digital Humanities research in Belgium, Luxembourg and the Netherlands	Belval, Luxembourg	9-10 June 2016
DARIAH	National events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austria • Belgium • Croatia • Denmark • France • Germany • Greece 	Various	Various

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ireland • Italy • Luxembourg • Malta • Netherlands • Poland • Serbia • Slovenia • Switzerland 		
Digital Past 2016	New technologies in heritage, interpretation and outreach. http://digitalpast2016.blogspot.co.uk/	Llandudno, Wales	10-11 Feb 2016
Lange Nacht der Forschung	Science night http://www.langenachtderforschung.at/index.html	Austria	22 April 2016
Borsa mediterranea del turismo archeologico	The Mediterranean Exchange of Archaeological Tourism http://www.borsaturismoarcheologico.it/en/	Paestum, Italy	27-30 Oct 2016
Digital Heritage	Annual conference hosted by the Centre for Digital Heritage http://arkdis-project.blogspot.co.uk/p/conference.html	Uppsala, Sweden	30-June – 2 July 2016

3.6.2 Publications

Scientific publications by partners concerning project work in academic journals will continue to be encouraged. Standard academic good practice concerning citation of authors is anticipated with the proviso that authors should:

- a) mention EU support for the work;
- b) notify the consortium of the publication;
- c) provide a digital copy to the consortium, to be made available on the website (if the publisher agrees with the Open Access Self-Archiving initiative www.eprints.org/openaccess/) or a link provided to an archive copy elsewhere; or to be kept in storage, if self-archiving is not allowed.

In addition to scientific publications, we anticipate that during period 3 the project will publish:

- Training materials
- Service specific brochures and fact sheets
- An updated project brochure

MiBAC-ICCU coordinates this task and, with support from PIN and UoY-ADS, will establish an

editorial committee for project publications such as reports, training materials and other literature. The membership of the committee will be convened from the project partnership or external experts as appropriate to the publication.

Material published by the project will be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution, Share-Alike, Non-Commercial licence. Publications will be available for download from the web site with printed materials being produced for distribution at events etc. Copies of project publications will be uploaded to the ARIADNE SlideShare account where possible.

3.6.2.1 Potential journals

Potential journals for publication of articles by project partners have been identified below.

Journal	Description	Deadline
Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage	ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH) publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to the innovative use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in support of Cultural Heritage. We encourage the submission of manuscripts that demonstrate innovative use of technology for the discovery, analysis, interpretation and presentation of findings as well as manuscripts that illustrate applications in the Cultural Heritage sector that challenge the computational technologies and suggest new research opportunities in computer science. http://jocch.acm.org/	Quarterly
Archeomatica	A new, multidisciplinary journal, printed in Italy, devoted to the presentation and the dissemination of advanced Methodologies, techniques and emerging technologies for the knowledge, documentation, exploitation and conservation of cultural heritage. http://www.archeomatica.it/	Quarterly
Journal of Cultural Heritage	A Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology for Conservation and Awareness. The Journal of Cultural Heritage is devoted to: - Safeguard, Conservation and exploitation of cultural heritage - Analyses and preservation of biodiversity - Sociological and economical analyses - Computer sciences in Cultural heritage http://www.elsevier.com/wps/find/journaldescription.cws_home/620738/description#description	6 issues per year
International Journal of Heritage in Digital Era	The International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE) is a quarterly high quality peer reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Libraries. http://www.multi-science.co.uk/ijhde.htm	Quarterly
Archaeometry Workshop	e-journal http://www.ace.hu/am/indexe.html	
Hungarian Archaeology	e-journal http://www.hungarianarchaeology.hu/	
Digitalia	Digitalia: rivista del digitale nei beni culturali Digital and print Journal on digital cultural heritage, containing articles, projects, events,	Annual

	reviews, edited by ICCU http://digitalia.sbn.it/ in Italian	
Archeologia e Calcolatori	Since 1990 Archeologia e Calcolatori has been an international observatory of theoretical and methodological aspects of computing and information technology applied to archaeology. http://soi.cnr.it/archcalc/ edited by CNR In Italian	Annual
International Journal of Spatial Data Infrastructures Research	http://ijsdir.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	Annual

3.6.3 Guides to Good Practice

UoY-ADS is responsible for managing the expansion of the existing online publication of Guides to Good Practice relevant to the ARIADNE infrastructure. Work planned for period 3 includes:

- Publication of new guidelines for:
 - 3D Datasets
 - RTI Datasets
- Publication of new case studies applying good practices to datasets held by ARIADNE partners
- Publication of a case study to accompany the Guide to Dendrochronological data in Archaeology.
- Cross-referencing of existing guidelines held by ADS, DANS and DAI
- Collaboration with the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D ICONS projects to align and reference their publications with those in preparation by ARIADNE

Electronic copies of Guides will be published under a Creative Commons Attribution, Share-Alike, Non-Commercial licence. The Guides will be published on the ADS website as part of the existing series; a page will be created on the ARIADNE site where details of the guides and links to the content can be made available to ARIADNE users.

News about the preparation and publication of the Guides and Case Studies by ARIADNE and related publications by the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D ICONS projects will be disseminated via project news channels.

3.7 Trans National Access and Training

During the third project period there will continue to be dissemination activity to support the promotion of the Trans National Access and training being offered by ARIADNE.

3.7.1 Physical access

Calls for participation in physical access to the ARIADNE infrastructure including summer schools and other access will be advertised in winter 2015-16 and spring 2016. PIN, supported by UoY-ADS, will lead the promotion of calls to invite European researchers to participate in physical access to the

facilities at PIN, Athena Research Centre and CNR. Calls will be advertised on the project website and disseminated internationally via the social media and news channels described above.

PIN, with the support of UoY-ADS, Athena Research Centre and CNR, will convene meetings of the User Selection Panel to assist in the process of reviewing applications for physical access.

News about summer schools and access visits will be disseminated through ARIADNE news channels. Researchers who receive ARIADNE funding will be invited to share news about their experiences and results.

3.7.2 Online Access

Integrated access to the ARIADNE online services will be launched during period 3. PIN, with the support of UoY-ADS, DAI, AIAC, DANS and all content partners will promote access to the online services. A series of news stories will be planned and released via the project newsletter, website and news channels.

3.7.3 Training

UoY-ADS leads this task with the support of PIN, DAI, Athena RC, CNR and AIAC. A series of activities are planned relating to the training of researchers in the use of the infrastructure portal. This includes a series of training workshops to be held during international conferences, which in 2016-17 includes:

- ARIADNE Data management workshop, OEAW, Vienna (19/01/2016)
- ARIADNE Data management workshop, ZRC-SAZU, Ljubljana (21/01/2016)
- CAA 2016 (2 April 2016) (confirmed)
- Athens expert forum (16-17 June 2016) (confirmed)
- EAA 2016 (30 Aug – 3 Sept 2016) (session proposal accepted)
- CHNT 21 (16-18 Nov 2016) (TBC)

These training workshops provide opportunities to disseminate news and information about ARIADNE and its services to participants. A set of information leaflets will be prepared for distribution during the training workshops.

Calls for participation and news from the training workshops will be disseminated via ARIADNE news channels and the social media.

Training materials and information leaflets will be made available on the ARIADNE website and via SlideShare, and their availability will be disseminated to researchers via the news channels.

3.8 Monitoring and evaluation

The dissemination programme will be monitored and evaluated to review:

- What messages (communication of benefits) are going out and who is seeing them;
- Whether those messages are being understood and remembered, and;

- Whether the messages are influencing opinions, attitudes and behaviours.

This information will help in planning subsequent phases of the marketing strategy, in developing future marketing activities and to revisions of this marketing strategy plan. It will ensure that the marketing strategy is effectively reaching the target audiences and they are taking action on the messages they receive.

Success indicators:

Description		Month 18	Month 36	Month 48
Stakeholder involvement	No of institutions	50	75	100
User involvement	No of participants	75	150	250
Project website	Visitors	6000	9000	12000
Research infrastructure online services	Anonymous users		400	800
Research infrastructure online services	Registered users		400	600
Social networks	No of members	500	1000	1500
Presentations at international events	No. of participants	1000	2000	3000
Good practice guides accessed	No. unique visitors	100	1000	1500
Newsletters	Readers	100	150	300

The following statistics are available for the project website and products such as the Guides to Good Practice:

- Page views
- Unique visitors
- Return visitors
- Visits
- Amount of time spent on the site/bounce rate
- Visitor's country
- Referral data (search terms)

4 Conclusion

This deliverable presents a progress report on dissemination activities during the second period (months eighteen to thirty-six) of the ARIADNE project, referenced against the second period dissemination plan (D4.3), and provides an update to the dissemination plan presenting our strategy for period from February 2016 to 31 January 2017 (months thirty-seven to forty-eight of the ARIADNE project).

In the second project period dissemination activities focused on raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts, building the stakeholder community and Trans National Access and training opportunities. Period 3 will focus on communicating ARIADNE's results, raising awareness and increasing the use of ARIADNE services and promoting awareness of good practices and "next generation skills".

5 References

Annex I – "Description of Work"-DoW

ARIADNE website: www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

ARIADNE, 2013, D4.1 ARIADNE website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

ARIADNE, 2013, D4.2 ARIADNE initial dissemination plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

ARIADNE, 2014, D4.3 First period dissemination report and second period dissemination plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D4.3-First-period-dissemination-report-and-second-period-dissemination-plan>

ARIADNE, 2014, First report on users' needs: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

ARIADNE, 2015, D2.2 Second report on users' needs: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/content/view/full/1188>

ARIADNE, 2015, D2.3 Preliminary Innovation Agenda and Action Plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D2.3-Preliminary-Innovation-Agenda-and-Action-Plan>

Annex 1: Contact people

Each partner has been requested to identify a contact person responsible for disseminating and sharing news and information channels relevant for ARIADNE.

Partner	Contact person	Email
PIN	Paola Ronzino Stephanie Williams Csenge Kosztolanyi Kate Fernie Sheena Bassett	paola.ronzino@pin.unifi.it stephanie.williams@pin.unifi.it csenge.kosztolanyi@pin.unifi.it kfernie27@gmail.com sheena.giess@gmail.com
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Annex 2: List of dissemination activities in period 2

Events where ARIADNE Dissemination Materials have been distributed/displayed

Date	Place and Country	Event + URL of website	Note	Partner
September				
6	Dresden, Germany	CIDOC2014 Access and Understanding– Networking in the Digital Era http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/home/program-information/workshops-en	Tutorial on CRMsci and CRMarchaeo for 10 archaeologists	FORTH
10 - 13	Istanbul, Turkey	EAA 2014 http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/home/program-information/workshops-en	Workshop: Opportunities Within The Ariadne Network Session: "Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology", 16 presentations, incl. by English Heritage, SRFG and UoY. c. 42 EAA members	PIN, CNR, ATHENA CETI
12	London, UK	Semantics & Cultural Heritage meet-up at The British Museum http://www.slideshare.net/MariaTheodoridou/london-meetup2014-mappingchi2cidoccrm	Presentation of Mapping the dFMRÖ coin database to CIDOC-CRM TO C. 20 archaeologists, IT researchers Session "Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology"	FORTH, OEAW SRFG and UoY (co-chairs)
22	Rome, Italy	Final Conference DCH-RP project	Presentation of ARIADNE	PIN
29 – 2 Oct	Heraklion, Greece	CIDOC-CRM Special Interest Group Meeting http://cidoc-crm.org/special_interest_meetings.html	Presentation of CRMarchaeo: the Excavation Model, An Extension of CIDOC-CRM to support archaeological excavations to 15 SIG members	FORTH
October 2014				
2	Venice, Italy	Risorse digitali e strumenti collaborativi per le Scienze dell'Antichità	Distributed flyers	PIN
6-9	Darmstadt Germany	EG GCH 2014 http://diglib.eg.org/GCH2014/	Presentation of scientific papers and a State of the Art Report to c. 60 CH & IT participants	CNR

November 2013				
10	Prato, Italy	Joint workshop between PIN, and the ARCHES developer team (Getty Conservation Institute/World Monuments Funds and the Farallon Geographics team)	Presentation of ARIADNE activities and discussion about collaboration	PIN
13-14	Rome, Italy	ARIADNE symposium at International conference on Research Infrastructure and e-Infrastructures for Digital Cultural Heritage.	Participation at workshop – over 200 attendees.	PIN, KNAW-DANS, ARUP_CAS, UoY-ADS
20	Hague, Netherlands	Reuvenstdagen	Poster on national conference for Dutch archaeologists – c. 600	KNAW-DANS
28	Rovereto, Italy	Lo scavo archeometrico (the archaeometric excavation) http://www.agiati.it/ara_news.jsp?ID_NEWS=1129&areaNews=192&GTemplate=ara_home.jsp ,	Presentation of ARIADNE and the services CNR is developing to 50 archaeology professionals	CNR
December 2014				
2	Vienna, Austria	Austrian Days of Digital Humanities from ACDH at OEAW http://acdh.ac.at/de/savethedata-workshop	Workshop on repositories: paper about EDNA/DANS at workshop “Save the data” to c. attendees	OEAW, KNAW-DANS
January 2015				
18	Budapest, Hungary	Meeting at the Hungarian National Museum	ARIADNE presented to Gyula Forster National Centre for Cultural Heritage Management	NOK
February 2015				
2-5	Glasgow, UK	EAA 2015 Conference (http://eaaglasgow2015.com/)	Presentation of paper "The value of complementarity. Integrating traditional and modern ways in archaeological remote sensing"	ARUP_CAS
10-12	Oxford, UK	CIDOC CRM SIG	Presentation of the ontological models CRMarchaeo and CRMba	PIN

March 2015				
3	Rome, Italy	Workshop "Accesso aperto al patrimonio culturale digitale e linked open data: strategie, progetti e nuove opportunità", Roma http://www.otebac.it/index.php?it/22/archivio-eventi/260/roma-workshop-accesso-aperto-al-patrimonio-culturale-digitale-e-linked-open-data-strategie-progetti-e-nuove-opportunita	Presentation of ARIADNE	PIN
3	Nicosia CY	EAGLE Conference	Presentation of ARIADNE activities: Mapping Tools and Interoperability	PIN
6-8	Pompeii, Italy	Stvdivm Ad Observabilia Aperienda (STVDIVM) http://www.openpompei.it/2015/02/04/open-archaeological-data-in-pompeii/	Julian Richards, keynote on Open Data in European Archaeology	ADS
18-21	Lisbon, Portugal	EAC Archaeological Archiving Working Group http://european-archaeological-council.org/activities-and-events/annual-meetings/eac-annual-meeting-18-21-march-2015-lisbon-portugal	EAC annual meeting	ADS
30-3 Apr	Siena, Italy	CAA 2015 http://2015.caaconference.org/	Three presentations, two sessions and a workshop – over c.200 participants	CSIC, ADS, PIN, OEAW, ICS-Forth, ADS, USW
April 2015				
15-19	San Francisco, USA	SAA 2015	Presentation "ADS 3D Viewer: an example of open 3D real-time visualization system in archaeology" to c. 50 SAA members	ADS
21	Amersfoort, The Netherlands	National Conference: Digital Archaeology	Presenting ARIADNE and the Data Seal of Approval (trusted digital repository) – 40 Dutch archaeologists	KNAW-DANS
May 2015				
3-5	Rome, Italy	E-RIHS, European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science	Presentation of the ARIADNE project	PIN

8-10	Alun, Romania	The national symposium from Valea Alunului - 2nd edition	Archeological site or historical landscape - theory and practice in field archaeological research meeting – c. 200 attendees.	ARHEO
13	Dublin, Ireland	Awareness raising exercise with politicians (TD & Senators) of Ireland	Private meeting	DISC
13-15	Athens, Greece	Automatic Process Model Discovery from Textual Methodologies: An Archaeology Case Study	Paper at the Ninth IEEE International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS 2015)	CSIC
15	Lecce, Italy	Participation in the conference: Identità Digitale Unica	Presentation of the ARIADNE project	PIN
20	Nuremberg, Germany	CIDOC CRM SIG	Presentation of the CRMarchaeo model	PIN
21-22	Aarhus, Denmark	Digital Heritage Conference 2015	Presentation "From research archives to webbased visualization: the ADS 3D viewer" to c. 120 attendees	ADS
25-27	Valparaíso, Chile	5° Seminario Internacional de Patrimonio Cultural Inmaterial: Informática Cultural, http://www.infocultura.cl	Keynote "Humanidades digitales, tecnologías semánticas, y co-investigación en patrimonio cultural" to c. 150 attendees	CSIC
June 2015				
11-12	Deva, Romania	The scientific communications annual session - 135 years from establishing the history and archaeology society of Hunedoara's county.		ARHEO
26	Dublin, Ireland	Irish Archaeological Data: Towards a framework: http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13614576.2015.1113037	Presentation of ARIADNE & Irish archaeology data strategies to c. 300 attendees	Discovery?
July 2015				
8	York, UK	Digital Heritage Workshop 2015	Presentation: "3D Web-Based Dynamic Platforms in Archaeology: Combining offline and online datasets to gain new understanding of the archaeological record" – c. 40 attendees	ADS

14	London, UK	ISKO-UK biennial conference http://www.iskouk.org/content/isko-uk-conference-2015-knowledge-organisation-making-difference	Presentation paper on vocabulary mapping and linked data	USW
20-21	London, UK	Linked Pasts http://pelagios-project.blogspot.co.uk/2015/03/linked-pasts.html	Overview of ARIADNE project and work with Linked Data a Vocabularies to c. 75 attendees	ADS, USW
September 2015				
3-5	Glasgow, UK	EAA Conference (http://eaaglasgow2015.com/)	Two presentations: 1. sharing and reuse of spatial data within archaeology & Cultural Heritage 2. Standards for 3D documentation in archaeology	DISC, PIN
8-11	Rome, Italy	Reconstruction of the Archaeological Landscape through Virtual Reality: http://archeologiavirtuale.it/	Training on ARIADNE Landscape Services – 21 students	CNR ITABC
9-11	Santiago de Compostela, Spain	AARG Conference (http://aarg2015.incipit.csic.es/)	Presentation of ARIADNE and its relevance to remote sensing Data to c.100 attendees.	DISC & ZRC-SAZU
17	Poznan, Poland	Workshop on Extending, Mapping and Focusing CRM, TDPL2015	Presentation of new extensions of CIDOC CRM developed within the project	PIN
18	Poznan, Poland	14th European Networked Knowledge Organization Systems (NKOS) Workshop http://tpdl2015.info/workshops-list/workshop-networked-knowledge-organisation-systems-services-nkos/	4 presentations directly relevant to ARIADNE (USW on mapping work, PIN on CRM time modeling, DAI on mapping, PeriodO used for periods in ARIADNE (by one of their team)	USW
25	York, UK	YorkNight European Researchers Night	Demonstration of 3DHOP at European Researchers' Night. A mega event which aims to show that research is fun and influences daily life for all of us.	ADS
28 – 2/10	Granada, Spain	Int. Conf. Digital Heritage 2015 (http://www.digitalheritage2015.org/)	Presentation of papers and tutorial on 3DHOP. poster and paper: Aspöck, Edeltraud; Kopetzky, Karin; Horejs, Barbara; Bietak, Manfred; Kucera, Matthias; Neubauer, Wolfgang (2015) A Puzzle in 4D: Digital	CNR, OEAW

			Preservation and Reconstruction of an Egyptian Palace.	
October 2015				
1-2	Lecce, Italy	Workshop on "L'integrazione dei dati archeologici digitali. Esperienze e prospettive in Italia"	Presentation papers: "Il registry di ARIADNE e il modello di metadati" ARIADNE activities and achievements	CNR-ISTI PIN
2-3	Timisoara, Romania	INTERNATIONAL COLLOQUIUM COMMUNICATION AND CULTURE WITHIN ROMANCE SPACE – 4th edition – Personalities, Phenomena and Moments in the Evolution of Romance Space, http://ciccre.weebly.com/call-for-papers.html	http://www.arheovest.com/pdf/brosura_ciccre.pdf , http://www.arheovest.com/pdf/program_ciccre.pdf	ARHEO
5-7	Madrid, Spain	Segundo Congreso Internacional de la Sociedad de Humanidades Digitales Hispánicas (HDH 2015)	Papers "A Modelling Language for Discourse Analysis in Humanities: Definition, Design, Validation and First Experiences", "Teaching Conceptual Modelling in Humanities and Social Sciences"	CSIC
21-22	Benevento (Italy)	Int. Conf. "Metrology for Archaeology 2015" http://vcg.isti.cnr.it/Publications/2015/MBPCDS15/	Presentation of a scientific paper	CNR
29	The Hague, the Netherlands	Training on how to deposit your data at DANS	Presented ARIADNE infrastructure to these 8 researchers	KNAW-DANS
November 2015				
4-6	Florence (Italy)	7th Round Table on polychromy in ancient sculpture and architecture	Presentation of a scientific paper	CNR
10	Umeå, Sweden	CAA-SE 2015	Presentation of a paper where ARIADNE was one of the topics.	SND
26	Zwolle, the Netherlands	Reuvensdagen: http://www.reuvensdagen.nl/programma_donderdag_26_november.html	Presentation of ARIADNE in Session: Malta voorbij: nieuwe ontwikkelingen en initiatieven in Europa Hella Hollander (DANS):	KNAW-DANS

			Van je eigen achtertuin naar die van de bureu. 600 attendees.	
28	Timisoara, Romania	ArheoVest Symposium - Interdisciplinarity in Archaeology and History - third edition http://arheovest.com/symposium/arheovest_3.html	Presentations and papers on different eras and domains of research related to the archaeology field and ARIADNE to 200 attendees.	ARHEO
December 2015				
1-2	Buenos Aires (Argentina)	Workshop on "SCIENCE AND INNOVATION FOR THE STUDY AND CONSERVATION OF WORKS OF ART"	Presentation of CNR-ISTI activity on ICT & CH, including ARIADNE (invited talk)	CNR
15-16	Rome, Italy	Modelli Matematici Nella Conservazione E Valorizzazione Dei Beni Culturali	Workshop organized by the Italian Academy "Accademia dei Lincei", R. Scopigno invited to present activities on Visual data and CH	CNR
16	Dublin, Ireland	ARIADNE 2015	Update of ARIADNE Activities to DARIAH Ireland Group	DISC
January 2016				
19	Vienna, OEAW	ARIADNE Data management workshop	Data management workshop	ADS, OEAW, PIN/ 2culture Assocs.
21	Ljubljana, ZRC-SAZU	ARIADNE Data management workshop	Data management workshop	ADS, ZRC-SAZU, PIN/ 2culture Assocs.
28	Sofia, Bulgaria	Annual Report on ARIADNE Project to the General Assembly of NIAM-BAS	Description and work done	NIAM-BAS